

Expression of words whose meaning has changed through metaphor in Omon Matjon's work

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Abstract: The article analyzes the metaphorical meaning transfer of words with a figurative meaning used in the poetry of Amon Matjon.

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A very large number of words in our language are polysemous, because people use separate words for each new concept in their daily life. It would become impossible to keep them in memory. As a result, it would become difficult to use the language and it would gradually become unusable. That is why, in any language, an attempt is made to express unlimited concepts and ideas from various combinations of linguistic units that did not exist in the language before. Thanks to such an action, new meanings are imposed on the words that were previously in the language. As a result, words with multiple meanings appear.

In artistic work, poets and writers always try to use words in a new sense, apart from their original meaning. This is legality. Because the desire to use the pictorial possibilities of words as widely as possible, the need to create unexpected, unusual, new images, the need to give expression in a new way motivates creators to act in this way. Because of this need, it is unique to the worldview of writers, only in their works.

The meanings of words that are encountered, which have not become popular in the national language, extraordinary special uses - portable meanings of words are created. One of our creators who skillfully used such words is the famous writer of Khorezm region, Omon Matjon.

In the poems of Omon Matjon, we can find the use of words in a figurative sense more often in the verb group. We can see the proof of our words in Amon Matjon's poem "I pass through your door...":

Even if the autumn is spreading, the roads are hazaan,

Even the snow fills the whole being,
Even if I hit you, I'll be happy,
I will sit at your door for a day.

If we pay attention to the stanza, we will see at a glance the words that express a special meaning. For example, autumn's spreading of frost, snow's burying of existence, and the shrill laughter of the snow served to express the meaning of the words beyond their meaning in the text.

The polysemy of words and subtle nuances of word meanings are especially widely used as an important visual tool in fiction. In addition to their correct meaning, there are several ways to use words in different figurative meanings, such as metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, and synecdoche. Among them, metaphor is the most widely used type in fiction, and we can find it more often in poems.

Metaphor (from the Greek metaphora-transfer, extract, metaphor) is a transfer of meaning based on similarity, in which things and events are related to color, shape, action-state character, place and time. based on similarity. 3 The transfer of meaning in metaphor can be divided according to the similarity of shape, sign, place and action.

A lives in my mind,
The dawn is promising.
But its yellow color
In the morning, the sun comes and goes.

If we look at the verbs in the poem beginning with the lines “There is a daffodil living in my mind...”, it creates a general meaning outside of the text.

Combined with words that do not do. In explanatory dictionaries, the verb to live is "to live for a certain period of time; to live; means "to walk alive". But here it is not the meaning of itself, but the transfer of meaning in a metaphorical way. The verb to live here is used in the meaning of "to exist, to be preserved". The verb to promise is used in the sense of “to promise not to do something”. It is used here in this sense, but the characteristic characteristic of a person was transferred to the word “dawn” and formed a portable meaning. The word in the last verse is connected to the sun and forms a metaphor.

This wood misses someone,
He wears a flower on his head.
Waking up in the morning is sad-

He is feeding on tiptoe

The verbs used in the verses taken from the above poem "Separation" also have a metaphorical meaning. For example, the verbs to miss, to wear a petal, to wake up, to feed express an abstract concept characteristic of a human being, but in the verses, this meaning was transferred to inanimate objects and formed a mobile meaning.

In a metaphor, the meaning of the word changes, and the concept or image does not change at all, but its initial known sign remains. For example, folklore is the beginning of speech art. The word "head" given in the example is used in a metaphorical sense, indicating a similarity specific to the time and place, in the sense of the beginning of fiction literature, the first samples. Similar examples can be found in the excerpt from the poem "Autumn" by Amon Matjon:

A righteous person is always restless,
The paths of hope cannot be closed to him,
It's like a father in an old lip-lip movie
Beiz's son seems to be lost.

One of the words that give verses a special beauty and charm is the combination of the ways of hope. The word "way" in this combination is combined with the word "life" and represents the ratio of life to the passing time and the passing da describes it as a road, and here he uses a metaphorical transfer of meaning.

It is not wrong to say that the use of figurative words in our linguistics enriches our language. Because the number of words in our language increases as we discover and use the many meanings of words. Omon Matjon also used the same word in different meanings. Although its meaning does not express any concept outside of speech with the associated word, it served to increase the subtlety of meaning within the context. The examples given above can be a clear proof of our current statement of a person.

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